

La Manoeuvre In Diplomacy And Defence

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Abstract: The concept of a 'Gentleman's War,' historically rooted in propriety and genteel rules, has traditionally downplayed the critical importance of strategy and manoeuvre. As modern warfare demands more complex approaches, the French term 'manœuvre,' with its inherently feminine connotations, emerges as particularly significant. During the Russia-Ukraine conflict, female leaders are introducing additional dimensions to defence strategies, pushing towards strategic parity in global security discussions. These women are impacting policy and outcomes via risk assessments, alliance

expansion, and security arrangements in the Euro-Atlantic zone, offering a nuanced view of global security dynamics through the prism of "Ungentlemanly Warfare."

Bottom-line-up-front: The rising influence of Euro-Atlantic women leaders during the Russia-Ukraine War marks a unique convergence of female leadership tied by conflict, geography, and temporality. These leaders collectively influence defence studies, introducing a more adaptive, female-centred diplomatic manoeuvre that challenges traditional concepts.

Problem statement: How do the strategic contributions of women in defence and diplomacy challenge traditional manoeuvre concepts in war studies?

So what?: The integration of women into high-level diplomatic and defence roles introduces critical variances in strategic thinking that align with broader societal trends. Their distinct psychobiographical and behavioural traits add new dimensions to decision-making, prompting a necessary reassessment of traditional doctrines, such as manoeuvring, to better navigate the complexities of contemporary global security environments.

Gentlemanly Warfare

The concept of "Gentlemanly Warfare," once rooted in honour, chivalry, and aristocratic rules of engagement, has lost its relevance in the modern era of conflict. Traditional doctrines have faded from strategic discourse as hybrid warfare tactics, including cyber operations and psychological warfare, have reshaped the battlefield. Russia's activities in Ukraine represent a break from antiquated limits via uncontrolled aggression, institutional cruelty, and open crime.[1] The Kremlin's contempt for human life, as seen by its tolerance for high losses, demonstrates a profound lack of concern for its soldiers. Despite international scrutiny and criticism, the savagery continues unabated.[2]

Ukraine has committed to a manoeuvre warfare strategy focused on speed, agility, and disrupting enemy operations, all while carefully navigating the balance between a war of survival and upholding the rule of law. This approach reflects a broader commitment to caring for its residents, animals, and even Russian prisoners of war.[3] This strategy is consistent with Clausewitzian philosophy, which asserts that a nation defending its territory has a strategic advantage. In Ukraine, the advantage is inextricably linked to the people's strong dedication to their sovereignty. However, Ukraine's attempts

have been hampered by timidity and incrementalist backing from important allies, such as the U.S. and Germany, highlighting the flaws in their long-standing partnerships.

Against this backdrop, women are altering the operational environment by introducing notably contemporary flexibility to military and diplomatic operations; however, their contributions are critically underappreciated in extant research. This mismatch poses concerns, such as underestimating the influence of sex-based characteristics and behaviours, resulting in a general lack of readiness and weakened global security systems.[4]

Ukraine's European neighbours—particularly those headed by women—have played a critical role in helping Ukraine's defence, influencing the regional reaction to Russia's aggression. Gender-influenced disparities in foreign policy perspectives are significant determinants of these diverse approaches. Both men and women draw specific policy preferences from their overall postures and basic values regarding the international community, indicating a hierarchical organisation of foreign policy attitudes. However, the strategic and adaptable responses displayed by female executives and ministers in this conflict highlight the benefits of giving a platform to various viewpoints.[5]

Notably, the Euro-Atlantic security posture has been shaken by women-led edge-case policies: Former German Chancellor Angela Merkel's 2015 decision to open Germany's borders to wholesale immigration; former House Speaker Nancy Pelosi's behind-the-scenes manoeuvring to remove Joe Biden from the 2024 U.S. presidential race; U.S. Vice President Kamala Harris' involvement in the U.S. withdrawal from Afghanistan; and Italian PM Giorgia Meloni's emergence as a strong unitary leader among a lineup of weakened contemporaries.[6] These instances highlight the influence of female decision-makers in global security. As a result, security strategists must grasp and apply this concept to defence research. The continuous categorisation of female-led government into limited "gender" and "feminist" tracks heightens the risk of misinterpreting global security.[7]

Manoeuvre as Metaphor

The French word 'manoeuvre,' grammatically feminine, offers a view of how sex-specific traits influence strategy and military affairs. This linguistic detail reflects broader shifts in modern defence and diplomacy, where 'manoeuvre' serves as both a metaphor and an operational concept, capturing the

complexities of contemporary warfare. Framing 'manœuvre' as inherently feminine enhances the metaphor to probe psychobiographical and behavioural traits in leadership as more women ascend to executive political roles.

This perspective eclipses traditional masculine constructs of security, allowing female leaders to navigate the "double bind" of balancing femininity with leadership by leveraging sex-correlated traits in decision-making. Research indicates that women in foreign policy leadership are more engaged in conflictual diplomacy and often achieve more meaningful cooperative outcomes than men.[8]

There is a distinct class of women in executive and lead ministerial roles within the Euro-Atlantic region, unified by four key variables: 1) gender, 2) geography, 3) temporality, and 4) war. These variables create a unique cohort with significant similarities, giving way to a novel diplomacy and defence studies environment. This novelty is especially evident because most female heads of state or government are the first women to hold such positions in their respective countries.

In the Euro-Atlantic region, female leaders have been instrumental in predicting and responding to Russian aggression, enacting significant foreign and domestic policy changes and fortifying bilateral and multilateral alliances.[9] They have also effectively used digital diplomacy to enhance transparency and accessibility, representing a significant shift from traditional statecraft practices.[10] Unlike Merkel, who avoided personalising her politics, the women in question have generally embraced a public-facing approach.[11]

Since 2018, 18 women have served as presidents or prime ministers globally, with Europe leading in overall female ministerial representation at 32.5%. However, only 19 of 159 defence ministries are women-led, highlighting a persistent leadership gap in traditionally male-dominated sectors. Despite this, female leaders have been pivotal in securing advanced weapons systems for Ukraine and mobilising foreign aid.[12] The appointment of women as foreign ministers in several NATO countries has further amplified their influence in global diplomacy. By the end of 2024, 27 countries will be led by women, predominantly in Europe, marking a significant shift in international relations.[13]

Female ministers, especially in defence and foreign affairs, have amplified their influence on global diplomacy. They have played pivotal roles in expanding NATO's influence—exemplified by the inclusion of Finland and Sweden—and advancing Ukraine's candidacy for the European Union and

NATO.[14] Their approach encompasses collaborative leadership, strategic foreign policy, adaptive decision-making, value orientation, and multidimensional risk perception.[15]

Leadership in Modern Warfare

Traditional military doctrines are under growing scrutiny as warfare shifts from organised, 'gentlemanly' wars to complex, multi-domain operations. Female leaders, exhibiting an ungentlemanly approach to combat, implement novel techniques such as female conscription and the deployment of all-female troops in Ukraine, deviating significantly from Euro-Atlantic standards in defence and diplomacy. [16]

These leaders transform classic concepts into a contemporary framework that blends intellectual complexity with strategic compassion. Their approach, marked by collaborative strategies and ethical considerations, provides a modern interpretation of Clausewitz's "Conduct of War," in which troop formation and deployment go beyond mere power to include the strategic use of all available resources, including moral and ethical ones.[17]

The tussle between female empowerment and the quest for domestic approval presents unique challenges for women in diplomacy and defence. Schramm and Stark argue that an 'iron lady' is more likely to emerge under conflict conditions, with history offering a few salient examples. Golda Meir, Israel's Iron Lady, was praised by President David Ben Gurion as "the best man in government." Margaret Thatcher, the UK's first Iron Lady, consolidated her power and reputation during the Falklands War.[18]

From 2018 to 2024, women possessed 32% of total minister seats in Europe, although their participation in foreign affairs and defence is far lower, at 22% and 12%, respectively. Women in these crucial jobs throughout the pre-war and kinetic war years contributed substantially to foreign policy and defence choices.

Heads of State/Government	Sweden: Magdalena Andersson	Czech Republic: Jana Černochová
Austria: Brigitte Bierlein	United Kingdom: Liz Truss	
Belgium: Sophie Wilmès	United States: Kamala Harris (Vice President)*	Germany: Ursula von der Leyen, Annegret Kramp-Karrenbauer, Christine Lambrecht
Bosnia Herzegovina: Borjana Krišto	Foreign Ministers	Hungary: Anna Panzár
Estonia: Kaja Kallas, Kersti Kaljulaid	Austria: Karin Kneissl	Iceland: Pórdís Kolbrún R. Gylfadóttir
Finland: Sanna Marin	Belgium: Hadja Lahib	Netherlands: Kasja Ollongren
Germany: Angela Merkel	Canada: Chrystia Freeland, Mélanie Joly	North Macedonia: Radmila Shekerinska, Slavjanka Petrovska
Greece: Katerina Sakellaropoulou	Estonia: Eva-Maria Liimets	Spain: Margarita Robles
Hungary: Katalin Novák	Finland: Elna Voltonen	Switzerland: Viola Amherd
Iceland: Katrín Jakobsdóttir, Halla Tómasdóttir	Germany: Annalena Baerbock	Ukraine: Hanna Maliar (Deputy)
Italy: Giorgia Meloni	Japan: Yoko Kamikawa	United Kingdom: Maria Eagle, Penny Mordaunt
Latvia: Evika Siliņa, Laimdota Straujuma	Latvia: Baiba Braze	EU Ministers
Lithuania: Ingrida Šimonytė	Liechtenstein: Dominique Hasler	European Council President: Ursula von der Leyen
Malta: Myriam Spiteri Debono	Norway: Ine Eriksen Søreide	European Parliament: Roberta Metsola
Moldova: Maia Sandu, Natalia Gavrilița	Romania: Luminița -Teodora Odobescu	Foreign Affairs: Kaja Kallas
North Macedonia: Gordana Siljanovska-Davkova	Slovenia: Tanja Fajon	
Slovakia: Zuzana Čaputová	Spain: Arancha González Laya	
Slovenia: Nataša Pirc Musar	Defence Ministers	
	Austria: Klaudia Tanner	
	Belgium: Ludivine Dedonder	

Select Females in Diplomacy and Defence (2018-2024)

The policy changes and defence initiatives taken by these female leaders emphasise the increase in the representation of women in political and defence ministry roles. This, in turn, brings sex-based traits and

behaviours to governance. The critical observation is that modernised manoeuvring is prioritised over rigid adherence to static doctrines.[19]

Strategic Responses and Female Leadership in Global Power Dynamics

NATO and the international community have historically struggled to develop a cohesive deterrence strategy, resulting in an inconsistent ethical and moral stance on global security issues. NATO's hesitancy to pursue military intervention and its lack of strategic focus on managing potential escalation exacerbated this defensive malaise. Despite efforts to strengthen power balances along NATO's eastern border after Russia annexed Crimea in 2014, European nations faced challenges in meeting their financial commitments to collective defence.[20]

However, by 2022, a shift began to take shape, driven by leaders such as Metsola, Marin, and Frederiksen, who increasingly advocated for a more proactive and unified approach to European security. Their calls for a responsibility to protect (R2P) posture marked a significant departure from the past, including full-scale defence systems and financial aid, which dimensioned traditional European security framework operations.[21]

The Biden Administration's appeasement-lite approach to international relations—prioritising restrictions on Ukraine's use of weapons to avoid provoking Russia over fully supporting Ukraine's defence—has become increasingly apparent. Washington's entangled red lines, drawn with the collaboration of Germany's middling Olaf Scholz, have prolonged the conflict and resulted in the loss of hundreds of thousands of lives. This brand of non-escalation was ultimately exposed as a smokescreen when Ukraine took Kursk in August 2024, and Russia's nuclear rhetoric diminished.[22]

The issue of securing airspace over Ukraine (#CloseTheSky) has languished since 2022. This unprincipled restraint is due to U.S. National Security Advisor Jake Sullivan and his "Rocking in The Free World" boss, Secretary of State Anthony Blinken; European women have worked diligently to address the disparity in airpower.[23] In contrast, Frederiksen of Denmark not only secured additional funding for Ukraine but also escalated Denmark's commitment by supporting the delivery of warplanes. Meanwhile, Kasja Ollongren, the Dutch Minister of Defence, personally flew one of the warplanes to Ukraine, a striking gesture that resonated globally.[24] This bold act not only underscored the Netherlands' support but

also amplified the growing visibility of women in defence, fuelling viral conversations about their pivotal role in Ukraine's prospects for victory.

Diplomat or Diplomates?

The Russia-Ukraine War has been the apogee of female leadership in global affairs, notably regarding war management and strategic planning. This transformation in traditional diplomatic and defence roles reflects a broader societal pattern, where women are becoming increasingly pivotal in global leadership, and the line between diplomat and "diplomates" fades. Consequently, it becomes evident that the strategic contributions of women are reshaping not only current international relations but also the future trajectory of global governance. Throughout this war, security agreements between Ukraine and European organisations (e.g., NATO, EU, OSCE, etc.) have increased in number despite severe contentious elections and political uncertainty. European leaders Roberta Metsola and Ursula von der Leyen, dubbed the "queens of European diplomacy," successfully negotiated difficult re-elections, cementing their leadership in the EU and European Parliament.[25]

"One less plane" was former Chair of the Defence Committee of the German Bundestag Marie-Agnes Strack-Zimmerman's response to what will happen if Ukraine shoots down a Russian aircraft.[26] This moral clarity directly challenges the effect of the U.S. restrictions on weapons use, countering the stereotype that women exclusively prioritise peacemaking over strategic imperatives. Women who advocate for strength or pro-conflictual policies are often criticised as 'hawkish' more harshly than their male counterparts. For example, Kaja Kallas and Ursula von der Leyen were both rejected for the NATO head position—Kallas for being viewed as too 'eastern' and von der Leyen being labelled an aspiring wartime president.[27] However, both secured or held key diplomatic positions. Kallas became European foreign policy leader, while von der Leyen led the European Commission for a second term, emphasising their sustained importance in decision-making during the conflict.[28]

The Baltic Sisterhood—comprising Kaja Kallas (Estonia), Ingrida Šimonytė (Lithuania), and Evika Siliņa (Latvia)—exemplifies a unified and decisive leadership approach during these turbulent times.[29] These leaders have significantly bolstered their nations' security, with Latvia and Estonia dedicating 24.2% and 47.8% of their defence budgets to military assistance for Ukraine, respectively.[30] In addition to increased domestic defence spending and greater contributions to NATO, their efforts in reinforcing

physical and digital barriers have bolstered NATO's Eastern flank, safeguarding their sovereignty and reaffirming the alliance's strategic priorities.[31] Their use of public diplomacy, principally through social media, has diverged markedly from that of their male counterparts, showcasing distinct discursive patterns, sentiments, and priorities. Šimonytė was vocal in condemning Russian aggression as early as 2021, while Siliņa has consistently urged democracies to resist falling into Putin's trap.[32]

Sanna Marin of Finland demonstrated firm resolve by criticising the naivety of EU audiences and advocating for a more decisive stance against Russia. As Paris proposed a "golden bridge" for Putin's dignified retreat and Washington considered an "off-ramp"—both approaches aligned with Yang and Li's research on male leaders' conflict avoidance behaviours—Marin firmly rejected these strategies.[33]

Georgia's President, Salome Zourabichvili, has remained a key figure in the country's efforts to deepen connections with the EU. Despite heated political discussion and the threat of impeachment, Zourabichvili's leadership resonates with those who support Georgia's European ambitions. Her efforts may result in a historic transition for Georgia, even as she faces the possibility of becoming the country's last democratically elected president—a sobering reminder of the region's fragile democracy.[34]

Maia Sandu, President of Moldova, demonstrates the challenges and rewards of female leadership in a complicated geopolitical climate. Despite the ongoing turbulence and loss of sovereignty in Transnistria, which has been the focus of Russian aggression, Sandu has led her country toward further European integration. Her unreserved support for Ukraine and her trusted relationship with President Zelenskyy have reinforced her position as a pillar of regional stability, contributing to Eastern Europe's long legacy of strong female leadership.[35]

Since 2019, women have led Nordic nations that have joined NATO, such as Finland (Marin) and Sweden (Andersson).[36] Frederiksen of Denmark, for example, spearheaded 20 international aid packages for Ukraine and altered national legislation to allow for female conscription. Frederiksen emphasised that "NATO will not waver in its support for Ukraine" and pledged to continue providing substantial military support and training to bring Ukraine closer to NATO.[37]

Under the leadership of Defence Minister Jana Černočová, Czechia has initiated significant security measures, including an ammunition funding scheme and the deployment of seized Russian reserves to bolster Ukrainian sovereignty.[38] Smaller NATO member states, such as North Macedonia—now led by a female president—have significantly increased their defence spending, more than doubling it since

Russia's invasion of Ukraine. This surge emphasises their commitment to harmonising with NATO standards. Similarly, Latvia, which has a female prime minister and a female foreign minister, has boosted its defence budget from 221 million euros in 2014 to 967 million euros in 2023, while Estonia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, and Slovakia have made similar expenditures.[39]

Italy's Giorgia Meloni emerged as a preeminent global leader amid war and a highly contestable European election season.[40] Her political acumen enabled her to navigate multinational alliances and establish herself globally. At the G7 Summit, Meloni's leadership was both symbolic and strategic. Her choice of a pink Armani suit symbolised a contemporary, feminine approach to leadership, separating herself from the austere, fascist-leaning designs of the past. Her usage of social media, notably her fun #Melodi tweet with Indian Prime Minister Narendra Modi, strengthens her worldwide visibility.[41] Additionally, her strong concentration, precise techniques, and acute knowledge of her function and public image indicate high political acumen and astute messaging. This dynamic was evident during the European legislative elections and has continued to evolve through the strengthening relationship with Prime Minister Modi, whose landmark visit to Ukraine may well reflect her influence in fostering deeper bilateral ties.[42]

As the political landscape evolves, with pivotal shifts such as Pelosi's bold effort to unseat Biden and the dynamic changes in Israel and Ukraine, the role of female leaders is increasingly critical. Whether in power or as leading candidates in influential nations like the U.S. and Japan, these women collectively speak for over a billion people, driving priorities like increased defence spending, adaptive foreign policy, and discerning risk perception.[43] Their growing impact needs a closer look at leadership through the lens of psychobiography, relating their strategic moves to wider geopolitical implications. Understanding the psychological and biographical elements that influence female leaders is critical, as standard intelligence tests frequently ignore the complexities of their decision-making, resulting in substantial strategic misjudgments. For example, despite its technological superiority, China has failed to understand the intentions of foreign female leaders, emphasising the need to rethink intelligence, which is hampered by insufficient Foreign Policy Analysis (FPA) frameworks.[44]

Key Female Traits in Foreign Policy and Defence

Manoeuvre and its feminine influence in modern warfare require an expanded analytical framework. Manoeuvring, characterised by flexibility, precision, and deliberate intent, is increasingly influenced by the psychobiography of women in leadership.[45] Alongside earlier discussions on the impact of female-specific elements and the challenge of balancing femininity with authority, this emergence of distinct sex-bound leadership traits and behaviours has a potency.[46] Recognising various psychobiographies improves our readiness for current partnerships and expands our awareness of how these distinct behaviours impact decision-making. Recent research identifies a set of leadership qualities, behaviours, and cognates that are increasingly connected with women in prominent positions in security and diplomacy. These characteristics have been systematically categorised into domains that are particularly relevant to the poly-crisis of contemporary global leadership. Analysing these traits provides a richer understanding of how female leaders transcend traditional participation in international affairs, actively redefining leadership to meet the imperatives of modern warfare and diplomacy.[47]

A strong predilection for collaborative methods is one of the most distinguishing characteristics of female leadership in these settings. These leaders prioritise the establishment of strategic alliances through coalition building, inclusive diplomatic efforts, and international discussions. Such coalition building is critical for negotiating the difficulties of global diplomacy. By integrating a diverse range of stakeholders, female leaders guarantee that the solutions developed are comprehensive and broadly supported, laying the groundwork for long-term international collaboration.

Moreover, female leaders frequently differentiate themselves in strategic foreign policy by taking a broader, more holistic approach. Their solutions often account for ethical concerns, human rights, and long-term global stability. This emphasis on relationship-building and constructive international participation is consistent with the ideals of "smart power," a balanced approach that combines hard and soft power to achieve diplomatic goals. By combining governance imperatives with pragmatic strategies, these leaders create foreign policies that are not only effective but also deeply ethical.[48]

Another important distinction of women leaders in diplomacy and defence is their adaptive decision-making. The capacity to stay adaptable and sensitive in quickly changing environments is essential, particularly in the explosive battlefields of modern combat and international crises. Women leaders frequently demonstrate higher conceptual complexity, allowing them to combine various cognitive and

behavioural techniques. This flexibility enables them to negotiate the unpredictable nature of global conflicts with the agility required for effective results.[49]

A pronounced value orientation also characterises the leadership styles of many women in high-level positions. Their decision-making processes are deeply anchored in caring and moral principles, emphasising justice, equity, and human rights.[50] By ensuring that their policies are grounded in these core values, female leaders make substantive contributions to global peace and stability, enriching conventional strategic frameworks with a focus on the common good.[51]

Finally, female leaders are typically recognised for their smart risk perception approach. They handle risk with a rigorous appraisal of its repercussions, considering not just immediate results but also larger social, political, and economic ramifications. This methodical approach frequently yields more sustainable and thoughtful decision-making. In crisis circumstances, women leaders are typically willing to invest liberal resources to avoid underperformance, ensuring that military and diplomatic endeavours receive appropriate backing to fulfil long-term goals.[52]

These characteristics—collaborative leadership, strategic foreign policy, adaptive decision-making, value orientation, and interdisciplinary risk perception—form a composite sketch of leadership qualities that are particularly appropriate for the current geopolitical climate and should be examined using the FPA framework. FPA provides the means for systematically investigating how individual and group leadership characteristics impact foreign policy results. As these characteristics grow increasingly common among global leaders, they indicate a shift toward a more considered and adaptive strategy for dealing with the complex difficulties of international relations and global security.

Collaborative Leadership and Diplomacy	Prioritises collaborative approaches and coalition-building strategies, emphasising the curation of strong and deliberate partnerships adaptable to multilateral and bilateral contexts. Female leaders balance task-oriented activities with relational considerations, enabling them to build and sustain robust alliances. This relational emphasis supports their ability to foster strategic partnerships and enhances public diplomacy efforts, allowing them to navigate the complexities of international negotiations effectively. The focus remains on achieving goals while maintaining and strengthening relationships on the global stage.
Strategic Foreign Policy	Reflects the ability to craft and implement broad, clever, multi-modal strategies that integrate humanitarian considerations and long-term global stability into domestic and international agendas. Leaders who excel in this area revise and align policies across various domains, effectively balancing hard and soft power to achieve strategic objectives. Their approach ensures that outcomes are ethically sound and strategically practical, allowing them to navigate complex global challenges with precision and foresight.
Adaptive Decision-Making	Involves staying flexible and responsive in rapidly changing and ambiguous environments, particularly during poly-crisis situations. It emphasises resilience and adaptability, essential for quick, informed decision-making in modern warfare and diplomacy. Female leaders often exhibit higher conceptual complexity, integrating diverse cognitive and behavioural approaches. This capability enhances their ability to navigate complex challenges, ensuring that strategic decisions are well-informed and responsive to evolving circumstances.
Value Orientation	Integrates core principles of responsibility and accountability into leadership and strategic decision-making. Women leaders often strongly believe in their ability to control events, suggesting a keen awareness that actions have significant consequences. This orientation prioritises justice and safeguarding vulnerable populations (R2P), ensuring policies are rooted in these values. Leaders with this belief system enhance traditional strategic frameworks, contributing positively to global peace and stability by aligning their actions with a commitment to responsible governance and the understanding that their decisions can shape outcomes.
Risk Perception	Comprises a careful assessment of the potential consequences of decisions, considering broader social, political, and economic impacts. Female executives are often willing to allocate resources generously in conflict situations, focusing on preventing underperformance and ensuring that military and diplomatic actions are effectively resourced to achieve long-term objectives. This measured approach leads to more sustainable and well-considered outcomes.

Key Female Traits in Foreign Policy and Defence[53]

Contextualisation and Conclusion

The characteristics identified in this research highlight female leadership's unique contributions to security and diplomacy, hence boosting the flexibility and accuracy of international relations and conflict resolution frameworks that challenge and enhance conventional global governance paradigms. While the increase of women in these positions is noteworthy, the major focus should be on how their distinct leadership characteristics add a new dimension to the study of international relations. This change emphasises the need for a larger study focus that extends outside Euro-Atlantic contexts, notably by investigating the rise of female leaders after 2018.[54]

A cautionary note about "Ungentlemanly Warfare" is the possibility of terrible effects if decision-makers' psychobiographies are not thoroughly grasped. For example, Angela Merkel's immigration strategy, which was first portrayed as a humanitarian effort, resulted in huge demographic shifts throughout Europe, causing social and political upheaval.[55] Similarly, Ursula von der Leyen's immigration policies have sparked significant reaction, affecting the region's political scene.[56] Pelosi's behind-the-scenes manoeuvring has also been criticised for weakening democratic procedures, while Truss' brief and turbulent time as British Prime Minister demonstrates the dangers of mismatched leadership choices.[57] These examples demonstrate the necessity of understanding leaders' motives and decision-making frameworks in order to foresee the long-term effects of their actions.

Harris's operating code, particularly in contrast to other leaders, is marked by perceived social anxieties and a relatively low level of conceptual complexity.[58] Her thin record of achievement, burdened by the challenges of the Biden-Harris administration's immigration policies, and limited experience in key areas such as U.S.-China relations, underscores the weaknesses in her foreign policy approach. While not without potential, her contributions often appear constrained by a lack of strategic depth and notable security challenges. She accepts responsibility for the Afghanistan debacle as the 'last person in the room' during Biden's decision to withdraw, which had disastrous consequences: billions of dollars in abandoned military equipment, the tragic loss of 13 U.S. soldiers, the chagrin of NATO allies who had been part of the mission since 2001, the silencing and subjugation of Afghan women, a weakened U.S. posture globally, and the emboldening of malign forces, including Russia.[59] Allies should look at this as a case study of Harris' leadership potential.

Furthermore, she has continued to signal her misinterpretation of the situation in Gaza, therefore hindering a vital U.S. ally, Israel.[60] By qualitative standards, she would not fall in the category of high-

level female operatives in the international relations and defence domains. These formalised foreign policy judgments are part of a comprehensive and alarming dossier of incompetence, demonstrating her incapacity to negotiate complexity.

The use of gender as a critical lens in FPA is becoming increasingly important. However, conventional frameworks frequently fail to incorporate the perspectives and consequences of female diplomats and defence executives. As security studies progress, it is critical to identify women's participation not just as a question of fairness but also as a strategic asset capable of improving the success of global security plans, particularly through "La Manoeuvre."

Leadership psychobiography and behaviours can also highlight possible inadequacies in conventional intelligence models. Traditional techniques often highlight technical skills and may struggle to comprehend female leaders' complex decision-making processes when they differ from established standards. While some countries thrive in gathering technical intelligence, they may struggle to effectively analyse the strategic purpose of female leaders, highlighting the need for more complete leadership analysis.

Incorporating psychobiographical methodologies, cultural assessments, and multidisciplinary frameworks can provide more insight into female leaders' motives and strategies. These alternate techniques give a more comprehensive view of leadership, ensuring that assessments are particular, multilayered, and context-based. Integrating these characteristics into policy and intelligence frameworks can result in more sophisticated global security plans that are better prepared to face the challenges of the twenty-first century.

In today's complicated terrain of international warfare and diplomacy, female leaders use the art of manoeuvring in ways that differ from previous methods. By widening the scope of strategic thought, they confront the varied difficulties of modern combat and diplomacy while expressing their distinct viewpoints. These leaders help deepen our knowledge of power and leadership by managing global security concerns via collaborative methods, strategic vision, adaptive decision-making, and a strong ethical orientation.

Their effect shows a shift in how to think about "Ungentlemanly Warfare"—not as a dramatic departure, but as an evolution in strategic thinking that includes a broader spectrum of leadership styles. In this environment, manoeuvre goes beyond the military realm to incorporate alliance orchestration,

diplomacy, and ethical concerns, providing a broader framework for reaching strategic parity in a globalised world.

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